

How to measure the lateral wall angle width of cephalopod beaks

Cómo medir el ángulo entre paredes laterales de los picos de cefalópodos

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ABSTRACT

The importance of assessing the lateral wall angle (*LWA*) in cephalopod beaks for taxonomic purposes is discussed and methods to measure it are reviewed. In addition, a new simple mathematical method to derive *LWA* from the rostral length (*RL*) and the jaw width (*JW*) – two linear measures customarily taken on beaks – is presented. Instructions to easily compute *LWA* by means of a function set in a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and with the *R* programming language are given.

RESUMEN

Se analiza la importancia de evaluar el ángulo entre las paredes laterales (*LWA*) en los picos de cefalópodos con fines taxonómicos y se revisan los métodos para su medición. Además, se presenta un nuevo método matemático sencillo para derivar la *LWA* a partir de la longitud rostral (*RL*) y la anchura mandibular (*JW*), dos medidas lineales que se suelen tomar en los picos. Se proporcionan instrucciones para calcular fácilmente la *LWA* mediante una función en una hoja de cálculo de Microsoft Excel y con el lenguaje de programación *R*.

KEY WORDS: Cephalopoda, taxonomy, beaks, measurements, methodology.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Cephalopoda, taxonomía, picos, mediciones, metodología.

INTRODUCTION

Cephalopod mandibles or beaks have proved to be a powerful means for prey-cephalopod identification, as well as for obtaining additional biological and ecological information (XAVIER *ET AL.*, 2022).

Since the XIX century the pair of beaks was deemed a taxon-specific morphological trait that contributed to species char-

acterization (e.g., FÉRUSSAC & D'ORBIGNY, 1834-48) and became progressively better and better described (e.g., JATTA, 1896; NAEF, 1923). It was only in the second half of the XX century, though, that cephalopod beaks started to be methodically exploited for systematic purposes thanks to the pioneering studies by MALCOLM CLARKE (1962; 1980).

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Figure 1. A: examples of narrow (left-hand side) to wide (right-hand side) lower beaks; they belong (from left to right) to the oegopsid squids *Gonatus antarcticus*, *Alluroteuthis antarcticus* and *Architeuthis dux*; a blue-coloured arch subtends the lateral wall angle (LWA) (beak photographs after XAVIER & CHEREL, 2021); B: schematic drawing of a lower beak in frontal view; the rostral tip, the two jaw angles, the rostral length (RL) and the jaw width (JW) are indicated; C: set up to measure the lateral wall angle in an oegopsid lower beak.

Figura 1. A: ejemplos de picos inferiores ordenados del más estrecho al más ancho, correspondientes a los oegopsidos *Gonatus antarcticus*, *Alluroteuthis antarcticus* y *Architeuthis dux*; un arco azul subtiende el ángulo entre las paredes laterales (LWA) (fotografías de los picos tomada de XAVIER Y CHEREL, 2021); B: dibujo esquemático de un pico inferior en vista frontal; se indican la punta del rostro (rostral tip), los dos ángulos mandibulares (jaw angle), la longitud rostral (RL) y el ancho de la mandíbula (JW); C: configuración para medir el ángulo rostral del pico inferior de un oegopsido.

In order to take the most advantage from beak analyses, CLARKE (1962; 1986) fixed a whole set of measurements of morphological details, as well as the corresponding terminology, to geometrically

describe lower beaks, a method since followed almost universally by subsequent workers. Incidentally, Clarke decided to work on lower beaks only because they are richer in details than upper beaks;

such a decision was elicited by the unfeasibility to piece together into pairs the thousands of loose beaks retrieved from sperm whale stomach contents (Malcolm Clarke, oral comm. at the 29th meeting of the *Commission internationale pour l'exploration scientifique de la Mer Méditerranée*, Lucerne, Switzerland, 1984).

Among the several measurements, there is one that is often used as a non-quantitative descriptive element, that is the lower beak size of the angle formed by the two halves (right and left) of the beak rostrum, with its tip as the vertex and the jaw edges as the angle sides. This angle is usually qualitatively described as “very narrow” to “very wide”, a quality frequently referred to the whole beak, i.e. “narrow beak” (e.g., CLARKE, 1986) (Fig. 1A). Obviously, qualitative features are to some extent subjective, hence they may be inaccurate. CLARKE (1986) himself, however, instructed about assessing this angle measurement, though indirectly, by the ratio RL/JW , where RL indicates the rostral length (from rostrum tip to jaw angle) and JW the jaw width (“[linear] width of rostrum at the [jaw] angle” according to CLARKE, 1962) (Fig. 1B) (CLARKE (1986) also designated this ratio in the simplified form j/i). In general terms, as for lower beaks, narrow ones present RL/JW values as high as about 3, whereas wide ones RL/JW values as low as about 0.9.

Later on, KUBODERA (2005) adopted, among the distinguishing features of cephalopod beaks, the ‘lateral wall angle’, acronymized *LWA*, thus defined: “in frontal view, the angle between the lateral walls” (Fig. 1A). KUBODERA (2005) advised to accurately measure this dimensional parameter in degrees and, as for its actual assessment, suggested to use a protractor (goniometer), either directly on large beaks or indirectly on photographs (taken by a dissecting microscope when necessary / feasible) in the case of small beaks.

Recently, also CAPUA, VOLIANI & BARTOLINI (2025) adopted the measurement suggested by KUBODERA (2005) to discriminate lower beaks of many Mediterranean species.

The value of determining the lateral wall angle size is strengthened by the fact that this parameter appears to be quite conservative throughout the whole cephalopod post-paralarval development (XAVIER ET AL., 2022). Moreover, the rostrum is the most resistant part of a beak, so it is the longest-lasting part in predators’ digestive tract contents.

In certain cases, especially when beaks are worn out and some parts missing (generally, the wings), the accurate measurement of the lateral wall angle may help in specific identification especially within genera and families (for instance, compare with each other the two items of the Mediterranean sympatric co-generic pair *Histioteuthis bonnellii* / *H. reversa* and co-familial pairs *Todarodes sagittatus* / *Ommastrephes caroli*, *Todaropsis eblanae* / *Illex coindetii* and *Ancistroteuthis lichtensteinii* / *Onychoteuthis banksii*, where the first species’ beak is narrower than the second’s; author’s pers. observ.).

The assessment of the lateral wall angle by the RL/JW ratio is unfortunately affected by a significant bias. As a matter of fact, this ratio is correlated to the actual *LWA* expressed in degrees by an inverse sinusoidal function (see further, eq. [1]) (Fig. 2), that is to say RL/JW is not linearly proportional to *LWA*. For instance, when considering the same interval in terms of degrees between the angles $90^\circ - 55^\circ$ and $55^\circ - 20^\circ$ (all of them within the actual range of lateral wall angles) the difference Δ between the angle sizes of both couples is 35° , whereas Δ is quite different between the couples of corresponding RL/JW values (Table I): $\Delta RL/JW = 0.36$ and 1.80 respectively. Therefore, especially for “narrow” beaks, RL/JW is not a proper proxy of *LWA*.

Another source of bias in *LWA* assessment by both photographs and looking through a dissection microscope ensues from the inaccurate positioning of the beak so that the plane where the rostral tip and the two jaw angles lie (i.e. the three vertices of the triangle delimiting the rostral angle) (Fig. 1B) is not perpendicular to the observer eye, be it

Figure 2. Inverse sinusoidal function relating the ratio ‘rostral length/jaw width’ (RL/JW) to the lateral wall angle in degrees (LWA°).

Figura 4. Función sinusoidal inversa que relaciona la relación ‘longitud rostral/ancho de la mandíbula’ (RL/JW) con el ángulo entre las paredes laterales en grados (LWA°).

human or instrumental (dissecting microscope or photographic camera). Any tilting of the beak along its axis would cause a foreshortening error in the LWA measuring.

Finally, beak distortion, mainly due to dehydration, may cause some alteration to the lateral wall angle size, especially in small and “immature” beaks (see ROSCIAN ET AL., 2021) (as for avoidance of beak distortion, see CAPUA ET AL., 2025).

In this note, methods to measure/estimate lateral wall angles, LWA , in degrees are reviewed and an additional one is proposed.

REVIEW OF METHODS TO MEASURE LWA

The traditional methods to directly measure lateral wall angles, by a protractor or a goniometer, are reported here below. See also KUBODERA (2005) about the following methods.

- Photographic method – Since the protractor/goniometer cannot be used directly on beaks (maybe with the exception of very large ones such as those of *Architeuthis dux*’s, the giant squid, and *Mesonychoteuthis hamiltoni*’s, the colossal squid), the angle must be acquired either

Table I. Differences (Δ) between selected LWA values and between corresponding RL/JW values. LWA , lateral wall angle; JW , jaw width; RL , rostral length.

Tabla I. Diferencias (Δ) entre los valores LWA seleccionados y entre los valores RL/JW correspondientes. LWA , ángulo entre las paredes laterales; JW , anchura de mandíbula; RL , longitud de rostro.

LWA°	ΔLWA		RL/JW	$\Delta RL/JW$	
90°	-	-	0.71	-	-
55°	35°	-	1.08	0.37	-
20°	-	35°	2.88	-	1.80

Table II. Setting of EXCEL spreadsheet for computing the rostral angle width in degrees (LWA°) from the measures of rostral length (RL) and jaw width (JW). Once the RL values are listed in the first column and the JW values in the second one, the third one gives the computed LWA° by the formula inserted in its cells.

Tabla II. Configuración de la hoja de cálculo de EXCEL para calcular el ancho del ángulo rostral en grados (LWA°) a partir de las medidas de longitud rostral (RL) y ancho mandibular (JW). Una vez que los valores de RL se introducen en la primera columna y los de JW en la segunda, la tercera muestra el LWA calculado mediante la fórmula previamente establecida.

RL1	JW1	=2*DEGREES(ASIN((B1/A1)/2))
...
RL_n	JW_n	=2*DEGREES(ASIN((Bn/An)/2))
examples:		
3	2.8	55.63627857
3.2	3	55.90637377
3.7	3.5	56.4549047
↑	↑	↑
RL column	JW column	LWA° column

by a photographic camera with macro lens if necessary (large and medium size beaks) or by a photographic camera fitted to a dissecting microscope (small size beaks); hence, two lines are drawn from the rostrum tip to each jaw margin, in order to delimit accurately the angle and facilitate its measurement (Fig. 1C). This is a two-step method that includes the photographic enlargement of the lateral wall angle; it needs a photographic equipment and is comparatively time consuming. Photographic acquisitions, however, constitute sound documents for further research development, including data publication.

- Drawing method – The lateral wall angle outline may be projected onto a paper sheet by a camera lucida (fitted to a dissecting microscope in the case of small beaks) in order to be quickly drawn in pencil, possibly with the help of a ruler, and the angle soon after measured. This is also a two-step method: it needs a camera lucida equipment but it is faster than the photographic method.

- Image analysis method – Several image analysis software applied to a digital camera connected to a stereomicroscope provide interactive measure-

ment functions, which include both length (RL and JW as for the present paper topic) and angle size measurement on a screen display (LWA as for the present paper topic); e.g., Leica Application Suite LAS X, device: Angle Tool (Leica, Wetzlar, Germany); ImageJ, open source software (US National Institutes of Health and the Laboratory for Optical and Computational Instrumentation, LOCI, University of Wisconsin).

This method is particularly apt to measure small size beaks quite quickly; a further benefit is the possibility to store acquired beak images with annotations; on the other hand, this system is based on costly equipment.

In all cases, attention must be paid that the lateral wall angle plane is perfectly perpendicular to the camera in order to avoid foreshortening errors.

A NEW METHOD TO MEASURE LWA

A new, indirect simple trigonometric method is here proposed. This is based on two routinely taken dimensions on beaks: the rostral length (RL) and the

Table III. Selected *RL/JW* values and corresponding *LWA* values computed by EXCEL according to formulas [1] and [2]. *LWA* values are given in both the decimal system (decimal degrees) and the sexagesimal system. *LWA*, lateral wall angle; *JW*, jaw width; *RL*, rostral length.

Tabla III. Valores RL/JW seleccionados y sus valores correspondientes del LWA calculados por EXCEL según las fórmulas [1] y [2]. Los valores LWA se expresan tanto en el sistema decimal (décimas de grado) como en el sistema sexagesimal. LWA, ángulo entre las paredes laterales; JW, anchura de mandíbula; RL, longitud de rostro.

<i>RL/JW</i>	<i>LWA</i> [decimal system]	<i>LWA</i> [°] [degrees & minutes]	<i>RL/JW</i>	<i>LWA</i> [decimal system]	<i>LWA</i> [°] [degrees & minutes]
0.6	112.9	112°54'	1.9	30.5	30°30'
0.7	91.2	91°12'	2	29.0	29°00'
0.8	77.4	77°24'	2.1	27.6	27°36'
0.9	67.5	67°30'	2.2	26.3	26°18'
1	60.0	60°00'	2.3	25.1	25°06'
1.1	54.1	54°06'	2.4	24.1	24°06'
1.2	49.3	49°18'	2.5	23.1	23°06'
1.3	45.3	45°18'	2.6	22.2	22°12'
1.4	41.9	41°54'	2.7	21.4	21°24'
1.5	39.0	39°00'	2.8	20.6	20°36'
1.6	36.4	36°24'	2.9	19.9	19°54'
1.7	34.2	34°12'	3	19.2	19°12'
1.8	32.3	32°18'			

distance between jaw angles or jaw width (*JW*). They are customarily taken either directly on sufficiently large beaks or by a dissecting microscope either provided with a micrometric ocular lens or with a camera provided with an image analyzer system capable of taking measurements, that is evaluating distances between two points of the item under observation.

Once obtained *RL* and *JW*, the computed lateral wall angle *LWA*[°], is derived by the equation:

$$LWA^\circ = 2 \cdot 180/\pi \cdot \arcsin(JW/2RL) \quad [1]$$

This equation may be easily computed using the Microsoft EXCEL compound function set as follows:

$$LWA^\circ = 2 * \text{DEGREES}(\text{ASIN}((JW/RL)/2)) \quad [2]$$

After listing the series of *RL* and *JW* data (in any size unit, as long as it is the same for both measures) into two columns of an EXCEL matrix, the computed lateral wall angle size *LWA*[°]

expressed in degrees will be automatically calculated in a third column where the above formula [2] is set (Table II).

Note that EXCEL functions names vary between different language versions. Therefore, the colleagues that want to apply the trigonometric method herein presented are advised to check the name of the functions in their own EXCEL program. The functions necessary for the present method are:

1. the arcsine function, which is the sine of the lateral wall angle expressed in radians (English EXCEL function abbreviation: ASIN);

2. function converting an angle value expressed in radians into the angle value expressed in degrees (English EXCEL function abbreviation: DEGREES).

As for the computation of the lateral wall angle *LWA*[°], the same results may be achieved using the *R* programming language (R Core Team, 2025) instead of the above EXCEL procedure. Introduce the *RL* and *JW* values as numerical vectors in RStudio. Once this is done,

Figure 3. Graphic method to estimate the lateral wall angle (LWA°). In the present example, $RL = 2$, $JW = 1.4$, therefore $RL/JW = 1.43$; to this value fitted on the ordinate axis, the corresponding the LWA° value = 41° can be read on the abscissa axis.

Figura 3. Método gráfico para estimar el ángulo entre las paredes laterales (LWA°). En el presente ejemplo, $RL = 2$, $JW = 1,4$; por lo tanto, $RL/JW = 1,43$; al ajustar este valor en el eje de ordenadas, se obtiene el valor correspondiente de $LWA^\circ = 41^\circ$ en el eje de abscisas.

the LWA° value can be obtained through the next script:

$$\alpha < -2 * \text{asin}((JW / RL) / 2) * 180 / \pi \quad [3]$$

In order to facilitate the computation of LWA size values, Table III reports their correspondence to selected RL/JW values, within the LWA range 20° - 110° . Moreover, the LWA size may be also estimated graphically by fitting any RL/JW value to the RL/JW vs. LWA curve (Fig. 3).

DISCUSSION

The trigonometric method to estimate lateral wall angles is quite fast and provides sound LWA estimates once either the compound function [2] or [3] is set in the EXCEL or RStudio program, respectively. Moreover, to be implemented, it does not need any special

equipment, especially when dealing with medium and large size beaks. Lastly, the here proposed method may be applied to data from previous records of RL and JW values.

This method is particularly relevant to decapodiform lower beaks because of their conformation, but can be applied to upper beaks as well.

A caveat: any error in measuring RL and JW , other than little ones, will reflect on the computed LWA° . If both RL and JW are either overestimated or underestimated, LWA° will be little affected. On the contrary, if RL is overestimated and JW underestimated, LWA° will be underestimated; if RL is underestimated and JW overestimated, LWA° will be overestimated. When working on medium/large samples of beaks from one species with the aim of deriving its mean LWA° value, little accidental measuring errors – apart any bias

due to systematic measuring errors (for instance, when all *RL*s are overestimated and all *JW*s underestimated or vice versa) – will be “incorporated” into the standard deviation of the mean since it is just based on all deviates (individual deviations) from the mean (LWA°_i – mean *LWA*), due to both natural variability and measuring errors (SOKAL & ROHLF, 2012).

To conclude, measuring the lateral wall angle provides a further parameter useful for identification purposes. Furthermore, *LWA* may be also used in both systematics and ecological studies (see ROSCIAN ET AL., 2022; SÁNCHEZ-MÁRQUEZ ET AL., 2023).

Although, as shown above, the ratio *RL/JW* is not a sound proxy of *LWA* because affected by bias, the same mea-

sures *RL* and *JW* can be used to estimate the actual *LWA*[°] by the trigonometric method here proposed, so that *RL/JW* values retrieved from previous works to distinguish species and genera from each other, first of all CLARKE (1986), can be used to estimate *LWA*[°].

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